

16. Agroforestry for the Green Deal transition - EURAF 2022 Summary

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The European Agroforestry Federation is an NGO, established in Paris on 16/11/2012 (W343014937 & Transparency Register 913270437706-82). It aims “to promote the adoption of agroforestry practices across Europe by supporting efforts to develop awareness, education, research, policy making and investments which foster the use of trees on farms”. It has a network of 31 affiliated entities in 23 countries.

The [Sixth European Agroforestry Conference](#) took place in Nuoro Sardinia from 16-20th May 2022. This briefing offers easy access to the conference abstracts. These have been collated into **4 TOPICS** and **13 SUBTOPICS**. Many of the abstracts are relevant to the European Green Deal, and to a **range of agricultural, forestry and environmental policies in the EU** and globally. To see the recorded oral presentations go to the conference link above. Plenary contributions were made on the following themes:

- [Ps.01](#) National policy commitments to support agroforestry in Italy
- [Ps.02](#) A social-ecological agenda for agroforestry in the Mediterranean region
- [Ps.03](#) Digital agriculture : threat or opportunity for agroforestry?
- [Ps.04](#) Research and Innovation towards the sustainable development of silvopastoral systems

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